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**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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Green Neighborhood Implementation Based On Comparative Study of Rating Tools Greenship Neighborhood Indonesia, Green Mark for Districts, and GBI Township

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Abstract. To determine the green level of a city (sustainable city), certain references or standards are needed that are positioned at an understandable and measurable level. Indonesia already has a green area reference standard that aims to create a sustainable area through Greenship Neighborhood. However, since the beginning of 2016 - 2021 (4 years) there is only one area that has received Greenship Neighborhood certification. Learning from several countries regarding the application of green area criteria can be used as a reference in developing green area criteria (Greenship Neighborhood) in Indonesia.

This study aims to measure the level of sustainability of Greenship Neighborhood Version 1.0 based on the comparative value of regional green Rating tools, so that it can be used to provide direction in designing sustainable green cities. The Comparative Method was used to compare the Green Mark for Districts Singapore, GBI Township Malaysia and Greenship Neighborhood Indonesia tools.

Based on the results of the comparison, the two assessment tools, Green Mark and GBI, have the highest points in the Green Open Space category, while Greenship has the highest points in the Green Community category. Greenship Neighborhood Version 1.0 haven't explained several indicators of green city theory (Green Neighborhood).

Keywords: Green Rating Tools, Komparasi, Green Neighborhood, Sustainable

1. Introduction

A city will experience developed over time. In the Green City Guidelines published by UCD Urban Institute Ireland, it is explained that the green city concept is an effort to create a sustainable urban environment. The concept of a sustainable city begins with the effects of human activities on the natural environment. So it is important to provide facilities that include elements of biodiversity protection in the development (Nugraha & Heston, 2017). The city's development is not only to exploit the city for the benefit of its residents, but to provide a better quality of life. (Kusumawanto & Astuti, 2014).

Rejoni (2016), A green standard of a city must be positioned at an understandable and measurable level. Indonesia already has a green area reference standard that aims to create a sustainable area through Greenship Neighborhood. Greenship Neighborhood was compiled by the Green Building Council Indonesia (GBCI).

Each country has a different rating system in determining the green level of a city. Such as the BCA Green Mark for Districts green tool scoring system is the standard of the Building Council Association (BCA) Singapore. Green Mark for Districts Ver.1.0 was launched on 29 October 2009 and enhanced with Ver 2.0 on 1 January 2013. The Green Building Index Township is Malaysia's green city standard. GBI Township Malaysia Ver. 1.01 was launched in September 2011 and enhanced with Ver. 2.0 in June 2017. Indonesia applies the green standard of the city through the Greenship Neighborhood, which was

developed by the Indonesian Green Building Council or Green Building Council Indonesia (GBCI). The first draft of Greenship Neighborhood was compiled in November 2013, and Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0 was launched in January 2016. However, since the beginning of 2016 - 2021 (4 years), there is only one area that has received Greenship Neighborhood certification, Kota Baru Parahyangan received a Gold Certificate on 13 November 2020, thus becoming the first area in Indonesia to be recognized by the Green Building Council Indonesia (GBCI) as an area that has implemented a sustainable concept in the region and its surrounding environment. Meanwhile, Singapore and Malaysia already have more areas certified as green areas. In Indonesia, the Greenship Neighborhood assessment has not been applied as a standard or benchmark in designing an area to become a green (sustainable) area.

Every design decision will impact the environment. So that urban planning designs have an important role in achieving sustainability and to provide solutions to environmental problems.

Learning from several countries regarding the application of green area criteria can be used as a reference in developing green cities (Greenship Neighborhood) in Indonesia. Singapore and Malaysia can be used as a reference in the comparison of green area rating tools in Indonesia because they have similarities in climate characteristics.

2. Methodology

The research was carried out by comparing several green rating tools. The green rating tools that will be compared are Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0, Green Mark for Districts ver 2.0, and GBI Township ver 2.0.

2.1. Indicator Evaluation

Reith & Orova (2015) Environmental sustainability assessment system index (Green Neighborhood) can be seen from several factors: Healthy environment; Pollution and risks; Water efficiency and waste management; Material; Energy efficiency; Ecology; Sustainable sites; Management, quality of service; Economic aspects; Community.

Green area is clarified by the presence of Green City Attributes which consist of: Green planning and design; Green open spaces; Green building; Green waste; Green transportation; green water; Green energy; Green community.

Parameter	Variable	Sub Variable	Indicator
Green Neighborhood	Green Open Space	Healthy Environment	Good Air Quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of Environmental Parks / City Parks / Green Line (RTH) • Urban Forest
			Climate Change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parks/ Green Lines • Urban Forest
			Noise Reduction
		Ecological	Soil Protection
			Local Water conservation
			Enhance ecological site
			Protection of native biodiversity
		Sustainable Site	Connectivity to green spaces
			Reuse of existing buildings
			Density development
			Sustainable site selection
			Connection to the urban environment
		Community	Provide local identity
			Public space
Local uses/needs			
Green Building		Develop Green Building	
Green Waste		Implementation 3R concept	

		Waste management	Sorting (Waste Bank)
			Liquid Waste Treatment
			Waste Processing
		Material	Using materials with low environmental impact
			Using local materials
		Sustainable sites	Sustainable construction system
			Efficient infrastructure
			Sustainable construction
		Management, quality of service	Monitoring
			Integrated/sustainable design
			Government involvement
			Quality control
	Green Transportation	Pollution and risks	Emission reduction
			Sustainable sites
		Bicycle street	
	Green Water	Water efficiency	<i>Rainwater discharge</i>
			Urban Rainwater Management
			Water recycle
	Green Energy	Efficiency Energy	Energy performance
Renewable Energy Technology			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar energy • Wind power • Hydropower 			
Monitoring Energy			
Green Community	Community	Society participation	
		Citizen Community	
	Economic Factor	Improved economic welfare	
		Life cycle cost	
		Local labour	
	Business growth		

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. General Comparison

The general comparison shows basic information about the rating tools systems.

3.1.1. Greenship Neighborhood ver 1.0. The process of preparing the first draft of the Regional Greenship was carried out in November 2013 and launched in January 2016. The Indonesian Green Building Council (GBCI) is an institution that was established independently (not from the government) and is also non-profit. Committed to educating in the application of a green approach to the environment and as a facilitator of the transformation of the green building industry. Greenship is a system of assessment tools consisting of points of assessment aspects (ratings), each rating will have a category that each has a value (credit point). GBCI describes greenship into several types of aspects:

- a) Greenship New Building
- b) Greenship Existing Building
- c) Greenship Interior Space
- d) Greenship Homes
- e) Greenship Neighborhood

Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0 consists of 7 categories:

- a) Land Ecological Enhancement
- b) Movement and Connectivity

- c) Water Management and Conservation
- d) Solid Waste and Material
- e) Community Wellbeing Strategy
- f) Building and Energy
- g) Innovation and Future Development

3.1.2. *Green Mark for Districts Ver 2.0.* BCA Green Mark for Districts Ver. 1 was launched on 29 October 2009. The enhanced version 2.0 is effective from 1 January 2013. The Green Mark for Districts aims to promote and practice environmentally friendly and sustainable areas. The Green Mark for Districts benchmarks emphasizes energy and water efficiency; environmental-based planning; green buildings and green transportation.

BCA Green Mark for Districts complements other Green Mark schemes, such as Green Mark for Residential Buildings, Green Mark for Non-Residential Buildings, Green Mark for Gardens, and Green Mark for Office Interiors. BCA Green Mark for Districts has a land area requirement of at least 20 ha (200,000 m²), divided into categories of residential districts, commercial districts, and industrial areas or business parks.

In the assessment of the BCA Green Mark for Districts Ver. 2.0 is divided into several criteria ;

- a) Efficiency Energy
- b) Water Management
- c) Material and Waste Management
- d) Environmental Planning
- e) Green Buildings and Green Transportation
- f) Community and Technological Innovation

3.1.3. *GBI Township 2.0.* GBI Township Malaysia Ver. 1.01 was launched in September 2011 and enhanced with Ver. 2.0 in June 2017. The Green Building Index (GBI) is an environmental rating system developed by PAM (Pertumbuhan Arsitek Malaysia/ Malaysia Institute of Architects) and ACEM (the Association of Consulting Engineers Malaysia). GBI has several environmental rating system tools, including:

- a) NRNC (Non-Residential New Construction)
- b) RNC (Residential New Construction)
- c) NREB (Non-Residential Existing Building)
- d) INC (Industrial New Construction)
- e) IEB (Industrial Existing Building)
- f) ID (Interiors)
- g) T (Township)

GBI Township has six core categories that have been defined to encourage sustainable township development:

- a) Climate, Energy, and Water
- b) Environmental and Ecology
- c) Community Planning & Design
- d) Transportation and Connectivity
- e) Building & Resources
- f) Business and Innovation

3.2. *Index-based comparison*

	Green Mark for Districts ver 2.0	GBI Township Ver 2.0	Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0

Green Open Space	Healthy Environment				
	Good Air Quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of Environmental Parks / City Parks / Green Line (RTH) • Urban Forest 	GMD 4-2	CPD1	LEEP, LEE1	
	Climate Change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parks; Green Lines • Urban Forest 	GMD 4-2	CPD1, CEW1	LEE4	
	Noise Reduction			BAE 6,BAE 5	
	Lighting and illumination	GMD 6-6	CEW 2, EEC 10	BAE 3	
	Ecology				
	Ground protection		EEC4, EEC7		
	Local water conservation	GMD 4-2	EEC5	WMC 3	
	Enhance ecological site	GMD 4-5, GMD 4-7, GMD 4-8	EEC5	LEE2	
	Protection of native biodiversity	GMD 4-7	EEC2, EEC5	LEE2	
	Pollution and risks				
	Minimizing the impact of natural disasters (floods, earthquakes)	GMD 4-5	EEC 4		
	Handling the urban heat island effect	GMD 4-4		LEE 4	
	Fire risk management				
	Sustainable Site				
	Connectivity to green spaces (public spaces)	GMD 4-2	CPD4		
	Reuse of existing buildings	GMD 4-5	EEC1	LEE3	
	Density development		CPD2		
	Sustainable site selection	GMD 4-5		LEE3	
	Connection to the urban environment	GMD 4-1		LEE 3	
	Provide local identity	GMD 4-6		LEE 2	
	Quality public space	GMD 4-2		LEEP	
	Community				
	Local uses/needs			LEE5	
	Local food production <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban agriculture 		EEC6	LEE5	
	Management, quality of service				
	Monitoring	GMD 4-9			
	Integrated/Sustainable Design	GMD 4-10	EEC 9, CPD 6	LEE P	
	Green Building	Pembangunan Green Building	GMD5-1, GMD 5-2	BDRS	BAE 1
	Green Waste	Waste management			
	Implementation 3R concept	GMD 3-7	CPD7	SMW2	
	Sorting (Waste Bank))	GMD 3-5		SMW2	
	Liquid Waste Treatment	GMD 3-4		SMW2	
	Waste Processing	GMD 3-5		SMW2	
	Material				
	Using materials with low environmental impact		BDR1, BDR2	SMW1, SMW4	
	Using local materials		BDR3	SMW3	
	Sustainable sites				
	Sustainable construction system	GMD 3-2	BDR 4, BDR 7	SMW2	
	Efficient infrastructure	GMD 3-3		SMW3	
	Sustainable construction		<i>BDR4, BDR7</i>		
	Management, quality of service				
	Monitoring		BDR5	SMWP	
	Integrated/sustainable design	GMD 3-3	EEC3	SMWP	
	Government involvement				
	Quality control	GMD 3-3	BDR4	SMWP	

	Maintenance			SMWP
Green Transportation	Pollution and risks			
	Emission reduction	GMD 5-3	BDR6	MAC P1
	Sustainable sites			MACP3
	Sustainable transportation system	GMD 5-3	TRC1, TRC2, TRC5	MAC2
	Pedestrian street	GMD 5-3	TRC3	MAC P2, MAC 1
	Bicycle street	GMD 5-3	TRC4	MAC5
Green Water	Water efficiency			
	<i>Rainwater discharge</i>			WMC 3
	Urban Rainwater Management	GMD 2-2	EEC8	WMC2
	Water recycle	GMD 2-3	CEW5	WMC 4
	Water efficiency management	GMD 2-1, GMD 2-5	CEW4	WMCP, WMC1
Green Energy	Efficiency Energy			
	Energy performance	GMD 1-1, GMD 1-5		BAE3
	Renewable Energy Technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar energy • Wind power • Hydropower • Building Orientation 	GMD 1-2	CEW3	BAE4
	Monitoring Energy	GMD 1-4		
Green Community	Community			
	Society participation	GMD 6-2	CPD10	CWS3, CWS1
	Citizen Community		CPD 11, BSI 3	CWS1
	Safety		CPD 5	CWS 6
	Diversity of population		CPD 8	CWS4, BAE 2
	Economic Factor			
	Improved economic welfare	FMD 6-3		CWS2, IFD 3
	Life cycle cost		CPD9, BSI 2	CWS 2
	Local labour			
	Business growth		BSI1, BS2	IFD3

Based on the comparative analysis, several indicators that can be considered as forming other green areas are:

		Green Mark for Districts ver 2.0	GBI Township Ver 2.0	Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0
Green Open Space	Microclimate Optimization (Optimization of design through modeling and simulation, verification with field measurements of the main climate data before and after construction / simulation of regional temperature)	GMD 4-3		
Green Building				
Green Waste	Minimizing Cut and Fill (Encouraging a reduction in the amount of excavated material transferred or transported to the district by optimizing the use of excavated and dumped material during earthworks/land preparation for the district)	GMD 3-1		
	Garbage transport system (Use of odorless pneumatic conveying system, special waste conveying design to minimize interference/ odorless pneumatic conveyance system)	GMD 3-6		
	Green and Gracious Builders Scheme Certification	GMD 3-8		

Green Transportation	Alternative Transportation Options (providing charging stations for electric cars in all strategic locations such as: transit hubs, public amenities, commercial centers and other neighborhood focal points)		TRC 5	
	Shared Car Parking (Optimize parking facilities by reducing exclusive parking for buildings and avoiding on street parking.)			MAC 6
Green Water	Water efficiency in Landscape (Reduce water requirements by choosing drought tolerant plants in landscape design)	GMD 2-4		
Green Energy	Site Planning and Building Orientation	GMD 1-3		
Green Community	<i>Stakeholder Engagement, Feedback and Evaluation Survey and evaluation of occupant satisfaction</i>	GMD 6-1	CPD 11	IFD 1
	Smart Infrastructure (Future growth and maintenance)	GMD 6-4		
	Save Environment (Natural surveillance in public open space)	GMD 6-5		
	Local Culture Applying the local culture of the local area in the aspects of: a) Building architecture based on local identity, b) Supporting facilities for the implementation of local culture, c) Naming places/buildings/roads based on local cultural names, d) Conservation of historical buildings and/or areas, e) Local cultural preservation activities,			CWS 5

4. Conclusion

		Green Mark for Districts ver 2.0	GBI Township Ver 2.0	Greenship Neighborhood Ver 1.0
1	Green Open Space	23%	17%	15%
2	Green Building	11%	3%	6%
3	Green Waste	16%	9%	13%
4	Green Transportaion	6%	14%	21%
5	Green Water	11%	8%	15%
6	Green Energy	17%	6%	9%
7	Green Community	14%	12%	22%

Based on the comparison of the value of the Green Mark for Districts in Singapore and GBI Township Malaysia, the highest point is in the Environmental Planning category (23%). Based on the Green City Attribute category, it is included in the Green Open Space parameter. When compared with Indonesia, the related category is Land Ecological Enchanment. However, in Greenship Neighborhood Indonesia, Green Open Space or LEE points only get a percentage of 15%, which is the 3rd place in the priority assessment (after Green Community or Community Participation) and Green Transportation.

Based on comparative analysis through green neighborhood theory, the Greenship Neighborhood Version 1.0 haven't explained several indicators of green city theory (Green Neighborhood), such as: Ground protection, Minimizing the impact of natural disasters (floods, earthquakes), Fire risk management, Dencity Development, Monitoring energy and Local Labour.

Rating tools that are not in Greenship Neighborhood ver 1.0, but are in other rating tools can can be an example to develop greenship neighborhood ver 1.0:

- a) Microclimate Optimization
(Optimization of design through modeling and simulation, verification with field measurements of the main climate data before and after construction / simulation of regional temperature)
- b) Minimizing Cut and Fill
(Encouraging a reduction in the amount of excavated material transferred or transported to the district by optimizing the use of excavated and dumped material during earthworks/land preparation for the district)
- c) Garbage transport system
(Use of odorless pneumatic conveying system, special waste conveying design to minimize interference/ odorless pneumatic conveyance system)
- d) Water efficiency in Landscape
(Reduce water requirements by choosing drought tolerant plants in landscape design)
- e) Smart Infrastructure
(Future growth and maintenance)
- f) Save Environment
(Natural surveillance in public open space)

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